

HAZARDS OF LOCAL FAILURE IN BENDING OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH PANELS FROM POINT FORCES

I.G. Zhigun, R.P. Shlitsa and V.V. Khitrov

Institute for Polymer Mechanics, LV- 1006 Riga, Latvia

SUMMARY: Simple design formulae have been given to evaluate the flexural characteristics of a sandwich panel in three-point bending. The model modification has allowed consideration of distinctions in the deflections of face layers and hence the deformation of a normal as well as transverse normal stresses in the middle layer have been deduced. Local curvatures, bending and transversal stresses have been studied depending on the thicknesses of face layers and the transversal properties of a core in shear and compression. Hazard of initial failure from local moment stresses at the central section as well as transversal stresses at the support section and close to the panel end has been revealed. Comparative estimates for bending stresses refining the results of conventional designs have been obtained.

KEYWORDS: sandwich panels, design calculations bending and transversal stresses, loading points, boundary effect.

INTRODUCTION

Layered plates type of sandwich panels among a wide range of structures, offering promising scope for the use of composite materials are of interest for varied structure mechanics problems. The development of the approach considering details of a structure and composite behaviour of these panels will occupy our attention in the bulk of this work. The solutions were above all refined based on Kirohoff-Love and Timoshenko hypotheses, considering transverse shear, anisotropy of layers and their sectionally uniform distribution across stack thickness [1], [2]. Refined approach where the deflection in stack bending is a function of layer location across the thickness takes account of local effects and characteristics of panel edge fixing. Applied theory for discrete layered model considering deformation of a normal was developed in [3]. Values of Cylindrical stiffness (D) and stiffness in transverse shear (K) derived from the sandwich model [2] and obtained based on experimental deflection data will agree. Different situation arises in the assessment of strength properties: design assessment of panel strength in terms of ultimate normal stress of outer layer.

$$\sigma_x^* = E_x \varepsilon_x^*,$$

corresponding to the limitation on bending moment as large as

$$M^* = bh^2 \sigma^* E_f / (6E_\tau),$$

(where, according to symmetric structure sandwich model, its effective modulus in bending

E_f was derived from the formula $E_f = E_o(1 - \mu_V)^3 + E_x[1 - (1 - \mu_V)^3]$ and $\mu_V = 2h_1/h$, $h = h_o + 2h_1$, see dimensional parameters in Fig.1). substantively differed from the value M^* , recorded in experiment.

Fig. 1: Schematic of sandwich panel

The reason is attributive to the local bending of an outer layer under point force in three - point bending of sandwich plate. The following issue under consideration associated with justification of the procedure for deduction of the solution for point force action on a panel surface. Employment of the exact solution for a half-plane loaded by point force (kind of Flamman's problem or one of Lechnitsky in case of material orthotropy) is combined with superposition of boundary-value problem solution for the region "cut out" from a half-plane representing a beam or plate. Some results which concern three-point bending of a beam have been derived with the use of superposition technique mentioned in case of the uniform material and the orthotropy of elastic properties [4]. At the present work by virtue of inhomogeneity of elastic properties the cylindrical bending of a sandwich panel from point forces is considered relying on the refined method [5], based on analytical solution for variational problem on a sandwich plate. The bending of a face layer of the Kirchhoff's type and the transversal deformations of a core in shear and compression were validated through their energy estimate.

KEY DESIGN RELATIONSHIPS

In description for the bending of a panel, which dimensions and the scheme of three-point loading are shown in Fig. 1, the kinematic model [5] was adopted allowing for consideration for transversal deformation of a normal as the difference in deflections between face layers. With this point clear, the traditional solution part allowing for transversal shear was supplemented by this deformation factor together with a local bending of face layers and therefore the elastic potential for a layer stack has been deduced. The Euler's equations derived from the variations of four displacements have been solved by the Laplace transform as the most suitable solution technique in discontinues and point loads. Leaving out the details of the procedure described in [5] let us represent here the final solution form for the deflection difference of outer layers and their local curvatures.

Distinction in deflections at the central section

Key impact from point force at the panel centre is governed by the gap of the deflections of face layers in between. The normal stress $\sigma_z(0)$ within the middle layer is also determined by the difference $w_\Delta(0) = w_2(0) - w_1(0)$ accurate to the transversal stiffness coefficient of a panel. The relative value of this difference for the panel of a symmetric structure ($h_1 = h_2$, $E_x^{(1)} = E_x^{(2)}$) is defined by the following expression:

$$w_\Delta = -w_\Delta/q_0 = [\tilde{s}_0(\xi_1, \xi_l) - 2x_\alpha s_0''(\xi_l)]/[b_1 s_0(\xi_l)] \quad (1)$$

where displacements w_i and u_i are dimensionless (related to $h_1 + h_0$), by a prime the operation of derivation with respect to relative variable $\xi = x/(h_1 + h_0)$ is designated and the following functions are introduced:

$$\begin{aligned} s_0(\xi) &= (ch\xi \sin\alpha\xi + sha\xi \cos\alpha\xi)/2\alpha \\ s_1''(\xi) &= \alpha^2 sha\xi \sin\alpha\xi \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

which can be grouped together at the certain points as:

$$x_\alpha = -\frac{4}{b_1} \cdot \frac{s_1''(\xi_l) \tilde{s}_0(\xi_1, \xi_l) - s_0(\xi_l) \tilde{s}_1''(\xi_1, \xi_l)}{sh2\alpha\xi_l + stn2\alpha\xi_l} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{s}_0(\xi_1, \xi_l) &= s_0'(\xi_l) - s_0'(\xi_l - \xi_1), \\ \tilde{s}_1''(\xi_1, \xi_l) &= s_1''(\xi_l) - s_1''(\xi_l - \xi_1) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

For the dimensionless parameters the following notation is taken:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= h_1/(h_1 + h_0), \quad \xi_1 = l_1/(h_1 + h_0), \quad \xi_l = l/(h_1 + h_0) \\ k_1 &= m_z/[\mu(1 - \mu)], \quad k_2 = n_z/[\mu^3(1 - \mu)] \\ m_z &= (G_{xz}/E_x)(1 - \nu^2), \quad n_z = (E_z/E_x)(1 - \nu^2) \\ b_1 &= 24k_2, \quad b_2 = -2k_1(1 + 3/\mu^2), \quad \alpha = \sqrt[4]{6k_2}, \quad \alpha_1^2 = -b_2, \\ q_0 &= 6P(1 - \nu^2)/[E_x \mu^3 b(h_1 + h_0)] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where the panel width is denoted by b .

For infinite panel length $l \rightarrow \infty$ from (1) can be derived:

$$\lim_{\xi_l \rightarrow \infty} w_\Delta = [1 + e^{-\alpha\xi_1} (\cos\alpha\xi_1 + \sin\alpha\xi_1)]/4\alpha^3 \quad (6)$$

Mean and local curvatures

Expressions for face layer curvatures at the panel central section can be represented as:

$$w_1''(0) = -q_0 x, \quad w_2''(0) = -q_0(\hat{\xi}_1 - x) \quad (7)$$

where the dimensionless parameter for the doubled value of the mean curvature $\hat{\xi}_1 = -[w_1''(0) + w_2''(0)]/q_0$ is defined as:

$$\hat{\xi}_1 = \frac{\xi_1}{1 + 3/\mu^2} + \frac{sh(a_1 \xi_1) - sh[a_1(\xi_1 - \xi_1)]}{a_1(1 + \mu^2/3) ch(a_1 \xi_1)} \quad (8)$$

and for the curvature parameter of an upper face layer the simple notation can be deduced:

$$x = \hat{\xi}/2 + x_\alpha \quad (9)$$

where x_α is derived from (3).

In such a manner in the bending of a symmetric structure panel the mean curvature (8) depending on the parameter a_1 is variable with a core shear stiffness value according to (5), while independent on transversal stiffness in tension / compression, defining the parameter α . Face layer local curvatures by (9) are the functions of both transversal stiffness factors.

STRESS CONCENTRATION

To estimate the maximum stress in sandwich panel layers in three-point bending the central section $\xi = 0$ is considered wherein $\max \sigma_x$ existing, however in deducing $\max \sigma_z$ the support section $\xi = \xi_1$ is also added to the first one and for $\sigma_z > 0$ - the free face $\xi = \xi_1$. Stresses at these sections seem to be the most hazardous as governing the initial failure of face layers induced by a longitudinal compression (due to σ_x) or delamination (due to σ_z).

Bending stresses at a central section.

Revision of conventional design methods for stress σ_x calls for deduction the moment stresses caused by the local bending of face layers, which are added to average stress. Let us estimate the value of moment stresses and examine the difference between average stresses and bending ones derived from simplified sandwich models based on the Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis for the whole layer stack. The bending stress of a face layer at the extreme points of its section is represented as two components:

$$\sigma_{x,t} = \pm \sigma_{x,t}^M + \sigma_{x,t}^O \dots i = 1,2 \quad (10)$$

of which the first one is a moment stress resulted from a local layer bending:

$$\sigma_{x,t}^M = \mu E_x^{(t)} w_t'' / [2(1 - \nu_t^2)] \quad (11)$$

and the second - an average stress due to the longitudinal layer force $N_{x,t}$

$$\sigma_{x,t}^O = \langle \sigma_{x,t} \rangle = N_{x,t} / h_t = E_x^{(t)} u_t' / (1 - \nu_t^2) \quad (12)$$

At the central panel section in view of (8) the derivative $u_t'(0) = \pm q_0(\mu^2/12)(\xi_1 - \hat{\xi}_1)$ and the (10) will appear as:

$$\sigma_{x,t} = [E_x^{(t)} / (1 - \nu_t^2)] [\pm q_0(\mu^2/12)(\xi_1 - \hat{\xi}_1) \pm (\mu/2)w_t''(0)] \quad (13)$$

where the upper and lower signs of the first summand in the square brackets correspond to $i = 1,2$ respectively and the second - to upper and lower points on the thickness of face layers each.

Fig.2: Variation of mean across thickness of outer layer relative bending stress σ_x^O ($k = 1$) and the maximum bending stress by classical theory σ_x^{cl} ($k = 2$) at the centre of the panel with the relative volume of outer layers. $2l_1 = 5h$, $\sigma_x = (\sigma_x/P)bh$

The design values of the first summand in (13) can be related to the bending stress σ_x^{cl} calculated according to the classical Kirchoff-Love hypothesis for the whole stack [2] in view of the longitudinal stiffness of face layers $E_x^{(t)}$ and middle layer E_x^O . As the stiffness of the face layers increases (their relative volume $\mu_v = 2h_1/h$, $h = h_0 + 2h_1$) the disparity between the values σ_x^O and σ_x^{cl} grows up (see Fig.2). However with relatively thin

face layers in the material of HEXCEL/Al type [3], $E_x = 40 \text{ GPa}$, $E_z = 310 \text{ MPa}$, $G_{xz} = 138 \text{ MPa}$, $h_1 = 1 \text{ mm}$, $h_0 = 10 \text{ mm}$ this discrepancy may be neglected. Notice that the longitudinal Young's modulus E_x^O as well as the transversal one E_z is not involved in the expression for σ_x^O and, hence, the estimate of maximum bending stress by classical theory can be obtained taking account of the longitudinal Young's modulus E_x of a face layer only. To this must be added, whereas the transversal shear stiffness is ruled out in the σ_x^{cl} design in three-point bending, it appears in the expression for the σ_x^O evaluation and as G_{xz} increases by an order of magnitude the σ_x^O value grows up in the range of 35% at $\mu = 0.9$. Substantial correction to the values of average bending stresses σ_x^O is dependent on transversal stiffness in tension/compression E_z of the middle layer and is governed by the second summand in (13). Referring to Fig. 3 the stress $\sigma_{x,i}$, calculated for the central section by this formula, differs from σ_x^O in Fig. 2 as high as 1 - 4 times depending on section dimensions. Due to sizable distinctions between the relative curvature values $\alpha_1 = \hat{\xi}/2 + \alpha_\alpha$ and $\alpha_2 = \hat{\xi}/2 - \alpha_\alpha$ a symmetry about x axis in the location of the curves in Fig.3, obtained at $z = \pm h/2$ and $z = \pm h_0/2$ is nonexistent.

Fig. 3: Bending stresses at the central section along the surfaces of face layers versus their relative volume at $2l_1 = 5h$

Face layer moment stresses dependent on the relative parameter α_α favour the overload of the upper face layer in bending as compared with the lower one. Overload coefficient is dictated by the values of the moment stresses. Taking the form

$$k_m = \frac{w_1''(0)}{w_2''(0)} = \frac{\hat{\xi}/2 + \alpha_\alpha}{\hat{\xi}/2 - \alpha_\alpha} \quad (14)$$

k_m increases infinitely at $\alpha_\alpha \rightarrow \hat{\xi}/2$, i.e. in the special case that

the local bend of the lower face layer is absent: $w_2''(0) = 0$. Each face layer relative thickness (defined by the structural parameter μ_V) for a panel in the material of HEXCEL/Al type corresponds to a definite k_m value shown by the curve $k = 3$ in Fig. 4. At $\mu_V^* = 0.15$ the value $k_m = \infty$.

Table 1: Alternate versions of the transversal characteristics of a panel stiffness.

k	1	2	3	4	5
G_{xz} , GPa	0.00	0.14	0.14	0.14	1.40
E_z , GPa	0.31	3.50	0.31	0.00	0.31

Fig. 4: Overload coefficient k_m of the upper layer by moment stresses at the central section versus relative volume of outer layers at $2l_1 = 5h$

Increase in the shear modulus G_{xz} by an order of magnitude, see Tab. 1 and Fig. 4 at $k = 5$, as well as the decrease by a factor of 10^3 in the Young's modulus $E_z - k = 4$ corresponds to μ_V^* displaced to the right as compared with the case $k = 3$. At $G_{xz} = 0 - k = 1$, as for the infinite E_z value, the denominator in (14) has a nonzero value everywhere at $0 < \mu_V < 1$ and a change in the curvature sign of the lower face layer at the small μ_V is absent. The opposite signs of curvatures in three-point bending theoretically at the arbitrary values of transversal stiffness and layer thickness data are not ruled out, however, in practice it may be found unlikely. In such an event the regularity of an increase in the coefficient k_m as the structural parameter μ_V is reduced, see Fig. 4, can be used as far as a certain limit. The latter can be established from the test data for a panel of varied layer thickness. The elaboration of a theory that follows and the relevant design method of a bending behavior should give due consideration for a strain variation throughout the middle layer thickness, as has

been done in [3] using the numerical realization of the method.

Transversal stresses

In evaluating the transversal stress responsible of failure by debonding mechanism the greatest gap in the classical theory [1], [2] exists for σ_z stress as distinct from τ_{xz} . By the model [5] taken here the normal transversal stress at the panel centre is evaluated from the following expression:

$$\sigma_z(0) = - \frac{q_0 E_z}{1 - \mu} \cdot \frac{1 + e^{-\alpha \xi_1} (\cos \alpha \xi_1 + \sin \alpha \xi_1)}{4\alpha^3} \tag{15}$$

suitable for a span length $l_1 > h$. Notice, that the stress σ_z is unaffected by the shear module G_{xz} , and varies as $(E_z/E_x)^{1/4}$. The effect of a dimensional parameter μ_V on the stress σ_z at the central section is shown in Fig. 5. With a very thin face layer the stress σ_z increases infinitely defined by the multiplicity of a zero - $3/4$, when $\mu_V \rightarrow 0$. In the other limit case, when $\mu_V \rightarrow 1$, this degree is $-1/4$. Minimum σ_z value is taken at $\mu_V = 0.75$.

Fig. 5: Effect of the relative volume of outer layers on the transversal stress at the panel centre: $\sigma_z = (\sigma_z/P)bh$

Notice, that for the material structure of HEXEL/Al type the stress $\sigma_z(0) \cong (3/2)(P/bh)$. What this means is the shear stress $\tau_{45^\circ}(0) = (3/4)(P/bh)$ acting at the panel centre $\xi = 0$ over the area inclined at the angle $\pm 45^\circ$ to z - axis equals in magnitude to the maximum shear stress in three-point bending *max* τ_{xz} , calculated by the classical theory. Hence, in this situation the shear mode of failure caused by either normal compressive stress or transverse shear stress is equiprobable. Feasibility of a panel local failure by the debonding mechanism as a result of positive σ_z values depends within certain limits on a panel extent along x - axis, i.e. on a ratio - (panel length / span). The expression for evaluation of σ_z stress at the panel end $\xi = \xi_1$ can be represented in the following form:

$$\sigma_z(\xi_1) = - \frac{q_0 E_z}{1 - \mu} \cdot \frac{1}{2\alpha^3} \exp[-\alpha(\xi_1 - \xi_1)] \cos[\alpha(\xi_1 - \xi_1)l], \quad (16)$$

suitable for a span length l_1 , satisfying the relationship $\varepsilon \geq \exp(-\alpha\xi_1)$, where ε is an any preassigned small number.

Variation of a relative σ_z value at the panel end is represented in Fig. 6 by the curve 1. Asymptotic formula for σ_z , applicable to the analysis of this stress damping as ξ coordinate recedes from support in case of $l \rightarrow \infty$, is deduced in [5]. In the construction of the curve 2 in Fig.6 matching the case $l \rightarrow \infty$, the abscissa x/l_1 have been equated to the value l/l_1 for the panel of finite length. Fourfold increase in compressive σ_z stresses at the support of a panel in length $l = l_1$ in reference to the panel of infinite length and still further difference of positive σ_z values allows contention, that for a finite length panel the hazard of failure by debonding mechanism in three-point bending is more probable, than for an infinite length panel.

Fig 6: Variation of transversal stress at the panel free face with the relative parameter l/l_1 at $2l_1 = 5h$

In the prediction of initial failure by debonding mechanism the positive σ_z values should obviously be correlated with their negative values at the support and central sections, having regard to the ratio of material strength in tension and compression in the transverse direction.

CONCLUSIONS

By the elaboration of analytical method for sandwich panel design in bending the refined characteristics for face layer curvatures and transversal normal stress have been deduced. The advantage of the derived formulae for stresses lies in analytical estimation of the effect of model parameters on the design characteristic considered. This have been achieved via the separation of the solution into a symmetric and antisymmetric components. The first one defines the transverse deformation of a normal as well as the

transversal σ_z stress and is independent of transverse shear modulus G_{xz} . The local effects of reduction at the panel centre and supports were demonstrated to be comparable with the transverse shear effects resulting in initial failure via delamination. Boundary effect at a free panel face with the specific length of panel sections extending beyond the supports is the next factor aggravating the hazard of delamination due to positive σ_z values.

Expression for the bending stress σ_x was represented as the combination of symmetric and antisymmetric solution parts. Moment stresses of each layer exert primary control over the local bending in point forces. The average σ_x^0 stresses for the panel having relatively thin face layers were demonstrated to be equivalent to the classical bending stresses derived by the Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis for the layer stack as a whole. Revised shear correction to the σ_x^0 has been deduced in term of a mean curvature. Local layer curvatures have been derived in terms of a mean curvature and an additional curvature caused by the transversal reduction. Combination of the transverse stiffness properties in shear and compression entering respectively into these curvatures given section dimensions governs the overload coefficient of the one of face layers in a local bending. The formulae proposed and assessments deduced from them are usable both in a sandwich panel design and in an effort to determine the parameters of a simplified model bounding its scope.

REFERENCES

1. Allen N.G., *Analysis and Design of Structural Sandwich Panels*, Pergamon Press, Oxford, U.K., 1969.
2. Johnson, A.F. and Sims G.D., "Mechanical properties and design of Sandwich materials", *Composites*, Vol.17, No.4, 1986, pp. 321-328.
3. Thomsen, O.T. and Rits, W., "Analysis of Sandwich Plate Theory", *Proceedings Tenth International Conference on Composite Materials*, Whistler, British Columbia, Canada, August 14-18, 1995, Vol. V: Structures, Poursartip, A. and Street, K.N., Eds, pp. 35-42.
4. Tarnopol'sky Yu.M. Zhigun I.G. and Polyakov V.A. "Distribution of Shearing Stresses under Three-Point Flexion in Beams made of Composite Materials", *Polymer Mechanics*, Vol. 13, No. 1, 1977, pp. 52-58, (in Russian).
5. Polyakov, V.A., Zhigun, I.G., Shlitsa, R.P. and Khitrov. V.V., "Deformation Features of Sandwich Panels in Cylindrical Bending by Point Forces. 2. The technique devised", *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, Vol. 33, No. 1, 1997, pp.32-63.